

Possible Antifertility Compounds-Part II : Synthesis of 1, 2, Disubstituted Benzimidazoles

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Synthesis of new benzimidazole derivatives, derived from the condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine and *N*-substituted amino acids have been reported. Some of these compounds have been subjected to Mannich-type condensation to yield 1-salicylamido-methyl-2-phthalimido-alkylbenzimidazoles. Two compounds were tested for antiestrogenic activity and one was evaluated as a male antifertility agent but they were found to be ineffective.

SUBSTITUTED benzimidazoles have been investigated as metabolic inhibitors in chicken sperm¹, in bacteria², in poliovirus³, and in chicken embryos^{4,5}. It has been postulated that substituted benzimidazoles could interfere with the production of nucleotides because of their similarity to vitamin⁶ B-12. Later, 2-ethyl-5-methyl benzimidazoles were shown to inhibit Ribonucleic acid (RNA) synthesis in chicken embryo⁵.

Fig. 1

It has been observed that benzimidazole itself (I, R=H) has very low activity⁷. Substitution at position 2 of imidazole enhances the activity. The simple alkyl, alkenyl and aryl substituents in the position 1 increase the antiviral activity. But modifications to the fused benzene ring destroy activity^{7,8}.

Spermatogenesis was arrested by substituted benzimidazoles⁹ and by imidazoles substituted at position 1 by aryl group¹⁰. 2, 5-Dialkyl benzimidazole has been reported to reduce sperm motility¹¹. 1, 2-Disubstituted benzimidazoles also cause nervous system (CNS) depression in experimental animals. Substitution of a methyl group instead of phenyl in position 2 led to the lowering of CNS depressant activity⁸, and hetero analogs gave enhanced activity over simple aryl (e.g. phenyl, naphthyl) derivatives¹². In addition, benzimidazoles could be explored for abortifacient, because of their teratogenic effect on chicken embryo⁵.

The above studies prompted us to synthesize a number of previously unreported compounds, containing benzimidazole nucleus for antifertility testing. The position 2 was substituted with phenyl carboxamido alkyl and phthalimido alkyl groups. The phthalimido derivatives have been shown to inhibit fertility in male rats¹³. In few compounds, salicylamido methyl group substitution at position 1 was based on the previous observation that 1-hydroxy-2-phenyl benzimidazoles have the CNS depressant activity⁸ and imidazole substituted at position 1 by aryl groups has antifertility activity in male rats¹⁰.

Experimental

Phthaloyl/3:5-dinitro benzoyl-amino acids were obtained following the method of Vogel¹⁴.

2-Phthalimido/3:5-dinitro benzamido-alkylbenzimidazoles :

A mixture of equimolar quantities of *o*-phenylenediamine and *N*-substituted amino acid was heated in an oil bath at 100-105° under reflux for 3-4 hours. It was cooled and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) to remove any unreacted acid. A pasty mass was obtained which was titrated with petroleum ether (60-80%) and the crude product thus obtained was recrystallized from appropriate solvent.

Various compounds thus synthesised are listed in Table 1.

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TABLE—1 2-SUBSTITUTED BENZIMIDAZOLE

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	% Analysis (Nitrogen)	
				Calculated	Found
1.	2-[α(3':5'-dinitrophenylcarboxamido)-ethyl]-	94°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₅	19.7	19.1
2.	2(3':5'-Dinitrophenylcarboxamidomethyl)-	160°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₅	20.5	19.8
3.	2-o(3':5'-Dinitrophenylcarboxamido-phenyl)-	250°	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₅	17.9	18.4
4.	2-p(3':5'-Dinitrophenylcarboxamido-phenyl)-	190°	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₅	17.9	17.7
5.	2-Methyl phthalimido-	245°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	15.16	14.8
6.	2-[α-(phthalimido)-ethyl]-	220°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	14.38	15.2
7.	2-(1'-phthalimido-1'-isopentyl)-	228°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	12.61	12.1
8.	2-(1'-phthalimido-1'-isopentyl)-	250°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	12.61	13.2
9.	2-(1'-methyl histidynyl-1'-phthalimido)-	225°	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂	19.6	18.9
10.	2-[(1'-phthalimido-3'-benzimidazolyl)-propyl]-	105°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₆ O ₂	16.6	16.4

1-Salicylamido-methyl 1-2-phthalimido alkyl-benzimidazoles

2-Phthalimido alkyl-benzimidazole (0.006 M) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of ethanol by warming on a water bath. To this solutions, was added a mixture of formalin (0.012 M) and salicylamide in 10 ml of ethanol and a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid with constant stirring. After the addition was complete, the reaction mixture was further stirred for half an hour at room temperature and subsequently refluxed on a water bath for 4-5 hours. Ethanol was distilled off, and the crude product obtained was washed thoroughly with water. It was dried and recrystallized from suitable solvent.

Table-2 lists the various 1,2-disubstituted benzimidazoles.

female rats. The rats were ovariectomized under pentobarbitone (30 mg/Kg I.P.) anaesthesia and rested for one week. On the eighth day the rats were divided in three groups. The first group was treated with 10 µg/Kg/day of Oestradioldipropionate intraperitoneally for three days. Second and third groups were treated with 2-p-(3':5'-dinitrophenyl carboxamido phenyl) benzimidazole (A) and 2-(3':5'-dinitrophenyl carboxamido methyl) benzimidazole (B) respectively. These compounds were suspended in gum acacia and were given at the doses of 100 mg/Kg orally along with 1 µg/100 gm of Oestradioldipropionate for three days. Afterwards all the animals were sacrificed and the uterus was removed from each animal and dried at 60° (Table 3). From these studies it appears that the test compounds have no significant effect on the uteri dry weight. The administration of potential antioestrogenic compounds results in drastic reduction in dry weight, RNA and protein synthesis.

TABLE—2 1, 2-DISUBSTITUTED BENZIMIDAZOLE

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	% Analysis (Nitrogen)	
				Calculated	Found
1.	(2-methyl-phthalimido)	92°	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄	13.2	13.7
2.	2(α-phthalimido ethyl)	140°	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄	12.7	11.9
3.	2-(1'-phthalimido-1'-isopentyl)	170°	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄	11.6	11.7
4.	2-(1'-phthalimido-2'-isopentyl)	345°	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄	11.6	12.0
5.	2-(1'-methyl histidynyl 1'-phthalimido)	325°	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄	16.6	16.2
6.	2-[(1'-phthalimido) 3'-benzimidazolyl]-propyl]	235°	C ₄₁ H ₃₃ N ₇ O ₆	13.6	13.9

All the melting points are uncorrected. Percent yield 50-60%.

Biological Activity

Antioestrogenic activity :

The study was conducted in nonpregnant adult

Male antifertility screening :

1-salicylamido-methyl-2-(phthalimido-ethyl),

TABLE—3 ANTIOESTROGENIC ACTIVITY OF BENZIMIDAZOLES

Compound	Dose	Duration of Treatment	Total No. Animals of	Body Weight (mg)	Mean $\pm$ S.E. Dry Uterus Weight (mg)	Dry Uterus Weight Body Weight
Oestradiol	1 μ g/100 gm	0-3	3	188.3 $\pm$ 17.18	31.6 $\pm$ 6.6	0.16
Oestradiol+A	1 μ g/100 gm +100 mg/kg	0-3	3	202 $\pm$ 9.13	28.3 $\pm$ 5.9	0.14
Oestradiol+B	1 μ g/100 gm +100 mg/kg	0-3	3	205 $\pm$ 20.02	27.66 $\pm$ 3.3	0.13

A 2-*p*-(3' : 5'-dinitrophenyl carboxamide phenyl) benzimidazole

B 2-(3' : 5'-dinitrophenyl carboxamide methyl) benzimidazole

TABLE—4 MALE ANTIFERTILITY TESTING OF 1, 2-DISUBSTITUTED-BENZIMADAZOLE

Compound	Dose mg/kg/day	No. of rats	1 BW, gms	FBW, gms	Mean $\pm$ S.E. Sem. Ves., mg	V. Prost., mg	Testes, mg
Uninjected Controls	—	5	215 $\pm$ 4	272 $\pm$ 5	632.0 $\pm$ 60.5	256.1 $\pm$ 29.5	2809.8 $\pm$ 100.4
Vehicle	—	5	225 $\pm$ 5	289 $\pm$ 5	582.5 $\pm$ 76.2	306.2 $\pm$ 16.8	2805.0 $\pm$ 185.5
1-Salicylamido methyl-2 (Phtha-limido ethyl) benzimidazole	100.0	5	222 $\pm$ 6	278 $\pm$ 5	575.1 $\pm$ 115.5	302.0 $\pm$ 50.0	2811.6 $\pm$ 148.0

benzimidazole was screened for antispermatogenic activity in male rats. The test compound, dissolved in propylene glycol, was administered orally at 100 mg/Kg/day once daily for five days. The autopsy was performed on the third day after the last treatment. Seminal vesicle, prostate and testes were weighed. The results are summarized in Table 4. No significant change in organ weight and no effect on histology was noticed at the given doses.

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